

ELIXIR Italy TP: a success story

Success stories: our training activities

Success stories: training quality & impact

Contributes to the development of a strategy to assess ELIXIR Europe training Q&I over 200 institutions in 23 Nodes.

Quality assessment of training courses

> 700 participants in training courses (2015 - 2023)

Career Stage (Training Course from 2021)

Employment sector (Training Course from 2021)

70% respondents to questionnaires

Quality assessment of training courses

Responses to questionnaires from 2018- 2023

Success stories: projects & collaborations

Industry

Projects and collaborations

TtT programme & community building

Wiegiers, Luc and van Gelder, Celia W. G. Illustration for the paper "Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR".
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3593257

FAIR Training Focus Group

Learning Paths Focus Group

ELIXIR Italy TP: what next?

- ElixirxNextGenIT Deliverables
 1. Survey on ELIXIR-IT Platform & Communities training needs and training programme
 2. 20 training events
 3. Report on the Q&I assessment of training events
- ELIXIR Work Plan 2024-2026
- Paper training quality analysis
- Paper ELIXIR-IT TP

Our mission

We believe that quality bioinformatics training is essential to achieve excellence in life science research

Support researchers and professionals in acquiring specialized computational and data management skills

Spread across ELIXIR-IT member institutions a culture of good teaching and learning practices

Establish national and international collaborations

Create a thriving community of instructors

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

NextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023

**"Bringing together
Communities and Platforms"**

November 27th-28th

📍 CNR - Rome, Italy

Conclusions

CNR.BiOmics
BIG DATA FOR BETTER LIFE

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